

EARTH SCIENCES

MEASURES FOR THE OPERATION OF WELLS BY THE GAS LIFT METHOD AND PREPARATION, TRANSPORTATION OF NATURAL AND ASSOCIATED GAS AT GAS CONDENSATE FIELDS

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Abstract

Mandatory research and measurement complexes for monitoring development should cover evenly the entire area of the development object, the entire fund of observation wells. They should contain measurements of reservoir pressure for control and piezometric wells, measurements of reservoir and bottom-hole pressures, well flow rates for liquid, gas factors and water content of products for producing wells, measurements of wellhead injection pressures and injection volumes for injection wells, hydrodynamic studies of producing and injection wells in stationary and non-stationary modes, studies on the control of the oil and water contact, gas and oil contact, oil and gas saturation, technical condition of the wellbore by field-geophysical methods, selection and research of deep oil samples, surface rock products of wells (oil, gas, water).

The article considers in detail proposals to improve the system of collection, preparation and transport of natural, associated gas and condensate on the example of the Altyguyi gas condensate field. As well as the operation of gas wells, the condition and suggestions for improving the gas and condensate collection and treatment system. The resources of high-pressure gas, which ensures its preparation to the required conditions at the integrated gas treatment plant, corresponding to the calculated values of the inlet pressure.

The peculiarity of the operation of the gas processing unit (integrated gas treatment unit) at the current stage of field development and the need to maintain pressure at the inlet to the installation to ensure the required quality of export gas is considered.

Keywords: condensate degassing, aggregate, group metering unit, booster pumping unit, gas factor, perforation interval, associated gas, natural gas.

The operational and technical characteristics of productive oil wells of the Altyguyi field are given in Tables 1 and 2.

The flow rate of 24 fountain wells is 82-6 t/day, the water content is 1-30%, only the water content of 3 wells (№№ 7, 16, 18) is 73; 71; 77%. The gas factor is 205-1129 m³/t and the oil solidification temperature is 36-37 °C.

Table 1

Operational and technical characteristics of productive oil wells of the Altygyi field

№ wells	Method of operation	Horizon	Down-hole (m)	Interval Perforations (m)	Output (t/day)		Water cut Water cut, %	Gas factor m ³ /t
					Q _{fluid}	Q _{oil}		
21	fountain	NK-8	4007	4001-4004 3993-3998 3994-4000	17	16	6	401
3	fountain/ gas lift	NK -9	3757	3732-3778	19	17	13	309
4	fountain	NK -9	3770	3728-3740	40	39	3	289
7	fountain	NK -9	3758	3746-3750	26	7	73	461
10	fountain	NK -9	3674	3653-3662	24	22	8	513
11	fountain	NK -9	3868	3833-3839	53	37	30	349
12	fountain	NK -9	3740	3720-3726	60	58	3	501
16	fountain/ gas lift	NK -9	3875	3850-3857 3800-3806 3769-3775	7	2	71	1129
17	fountain	NK -9	3860	3842-3848	79	78	1	331
18	fountain	NK -9	3905	3890-3896	35	8	77	403
19	fountain	NK -9	3910	3891-3897	84	82	2	401
24	fountain	NK -9	3751	3691-2302	56	52	7	205
51	fountain/ gas lift	NK -9	3685	3652-3662	13	12	8	403
52	gas lift	NK -9	3685	3672-3679	16	15	6	290
102	fountain	NK -9	3727	3695-3704	37	36	3	332
104	fountain	NK -9	3760	3714-3723	17	16	4	612
105	fountain	NK -9	3860	3838-3844	56	55	2	250
106	fountain	NK -9	3810	3783-3792	43	33	23	283
107	fountain	NK -9	3885	3864-3869	40	39	3	318
108	fountain	NK -9	3829	3790-3796	35	33	6	303
110	fountain	NK -9	3820	3789-3791	12	11	8	513
111	fountain	NK -9	3880	3834-3842	71	70	1	283
112	fountain	NK -9	3771	3763-3769	55	53	4	374
113	fountain	NK -9	3705	3686-3695	7	6	8	726
114	fountain	NK -9	3700	3682-3691	44	36	18	403

Table 2

Operational and technical characteristics of productive oil wells of the Altygyi field

№ wells	Method of operation	Horizon	Downhole (m)	Interval Perforations (m)	$P_b/P_{ann.}$	Fitting diameter (mm)	Gas inlet depth (m)	Note
21	fountain	NK -8	4007	4001-4004 3993-3998 3994-4000	34/118	5	2200	
3	fountain/ gas lift	NK -9	3757	3732-3778	60/105	4		
4	fountain	NK -9	3770	3728-3740	44/106	8		
7	fountain	NK -9	3758	3746-3750	24/153	5		
10	fountain	NK -9	3674	3653-3662	76/154	6		
11	fountain	NK -9	3868	3833-3839	27/136	6		
12	fountain	NK -9	3740	3720-3726	153/248	8		
16	fountain/ gas lift	NK -9	3875	3850-3857 3800-3806 3769-3775	152/155	5		Puncher 2000 m
17	fountain	NK -9	3860	3842-3848	57/143	8		
18	fountain	NK -9	3905	3890-3896	15/116	4		
19	fountain	NK -9	3910	3891-3897	114/122	8		
24	fountain	NK -9	3751	3691-2302	118/144	8		
51	fountain/ gas lift	NK -9	3685	3652-3662	31/94	5		Puncher 2000 m
52	gas lift	NK -9	3685	3672-3679	46/76	6	2200	Puncher 2000 m
102	fountain	NK -9	3727	3695-3704	100/114	6		
104	fountain	NK -9	3760	3714-3723	63/154	4		
105	fountain	NK -9	3860	3838-3844	81/152	8		
106	fountain	NK -9	3810	3783-3792	122/136	5		
107	fountain	NK -9	3885	3864-3869	78/110	5		
108	fountain	NK -9	3829	3790-3796	63/115	6		
110	fountain	NK -9	3820	3789-3791	52/137	4		
111	fountain	NK -9	3880	3834-3842	57/148	8		
112	fountain	NK -9	3771	3763-3769	13/167	4		
113	fountain	NK -9	3705	3686-3695	70/112	8		
114	fountain	NK -9	3700	3682-3691	102/136	6		

In 2011, 2 wells (№№. 3 and 51) were transferred to gas lift operation. In 2014, due to the transition of these two wells to a semi-spontaneous mode of operation, the supply of a working agent was stopped [1]. And now these wells are working in a fountain way. During the operation of wells by the gas lift method, over time, there was a decrease in annular pressure, oil degassing and an increase in dissolved gas in the composition of the extracted products. As a result, this condition led to the transition of wells from the gas lift to the fountain method of operation.

Table 3

The proposed variant of the development of the transition
of fountain wells to the gas lift method of operation for the Altyguyi field
(basic option I)

Indicators	Unit of measurement	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027
Oil production	thousand tons						
Liquid extraction	thousand tons						
Associated gas resources	miln m ³						
Transfer of wells to the gas lift method	well		5	6	7		
Fund of gas lift wells operating until the end of the year	well	1	6	12	19	19	19
Average oil flow rate of operating wells	t/day						
by liquid	t/day						
Water cut	%						
Required gas resource for gas lift	miln m ³	1,9	5,9	30,2	32,3	43,1	41,7

(Option II)

Indicators	Unit of meas.	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027
Oil production	thousand tons						
Liquid extraction	thousand tons						
Associated gas resources	miln m ³						
Transfer of wells to the gas lift method	well		7	12	12	12	12
Fund of gas lift wells operating until the end of the year	well	1	8	20	32	44	56
Average oil flow rate of operating wells	t/day						
by liquid	t/day						
Water cut	%						
Required gas resource for gas lift	miln m ³	1,9	19,7	68,8	141	188	209

(Option III)

Indicators	Unit of meas.	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027
Oil production	thousand tons						
Liquid extraction	thousand tons						
Associated gas resources	miln m ³						
Transfer of wells to the gas lift method	well		11	24	13	7	6
Fund of gas lift wells operating until the end of the year	well	1	12	36	49	56	62
Average oil flow rate of operating wells	t/day						
by liquid	t/day						
Water cut	%						
Required gas resource for gas lift	miln m ³	1,9	11,0	45,4	88,7	120	120

Subsequently, with the time of reduction of reservoir pressure on productive formations, it will be necessary to restore the gas supply and switch to the gas lift method of operation.

Currently, 52 wells are being operated at the field. According to the calculations of the field development, the transition of all fountain wells to operation by the gas lift method is being considered.

Table 3 shows the proposed options for the development of the transition of fountain wells to the gas lift method of operation.

In the gas lift mode, the supply of the working agent in the range of 2000-2200 meters lifts are carried out at 38 °C with heated gas through the holes of the gas lift valves temporarily installed in place [2, 3].

At the field, gas is supplied to gas lift wells with operating pressures of 70-85 kgf/cm² by special gas compression lines. The gas consumption for each well currently averages 15 thousand m³/day.

To operate the lift with the greatest efficiency, i.e. with the minimum specific consumption, it is necessary that the lift operates at the optimal flow rate, which requires the greatest immersion under the dynamic level,

i.e. the length of the lift must be equal to the depth of the well. The minimum specific flow rate in the maximum feed mode is provided if the relative immersion is $\xi = 0.5$, and for the optimal mode the relative maximum flow rate is $\xi = 0.6$ [4].

Operated gas lift wells need to be optimized according to existing methods. According to calculations, in gas lift wells with a gas inlet point of 2300 - 2500, we accept a working pressure of $P_{work} = 6.4; 7.4; 8.4$ MPa, and in wells with a gas inlet depth of 3000 - 3500 m - 10-12 MPa. At gas condensate fields, it is necessary to implement a closed-cycle compressor gas lift with high-quality gas preparation for the needs of the gas lift and with further gas supply to the export gas pipeline.

The system of collection and preparation of products at the wells of the Altyguyi field is compatible with the collection and preparation of products at the wells of the Korpedje field.

The system of collecting and preparing gas condensate wells of the Altyguyi field is shown in the figure.

Figure. The system of collecting and preparing gas condensate wells of the Altygyi field

The products of gas condensate wells with gas pipelines are sent to a complex metering unit and from there they are sent through collectors to the first stage of the Korpedje complex gas treatment plant.

Let's consider the features of the energy technology complex of a gas condensate field on the example of the Western part of Turkmenistan, including producing wells, a collection system, a preparation system and compression of the extracted gas in the aspect of expediency (necessity) of modification (reconstruction) for the future covered by the field development project [5].

The compressor station (CS) provides:

1. compression of associated gas coming to the CS reception through the gas pipeline in three compression stages: from 0.3 MPa to 7.5 MPa;
2. compression of associated gas coming to the CS reception via combined gas pipelines from oil and gas collection points (DNC-1 and DNC-2) by fields;
3. compression of the natural gas of the gas condensate field itself, which is received by the CS through an incoming combined gas pipeline connected to the corresponding group measuring units (GMU).

The technical and technological features of the CS are also:

- the presence at the compressor station of two units (with cooling systems) of the first and second stages of compression of associated gas from an inlet pressure of 0.3 MPa to a pressure of 2.8 MPa, which is the inlet pressure to the terminal (third) compression stage;
- the presence at the compressor station of three units at the third compression stage, one of which is designed to compress associated gas, and the other two to compress natural gas coming directly to the final compression stage from the natural gas supply pipeline;
- the presence of a gas cooling system by low-temperature mechanical refrigeration, i.e. by low-temperature condensation, which is provided by generating cold on steam compression machines using a refrigerant - freon.

The gas resources that can be disposed of (sent to the consumer with the required gas quality) through the CS are unambiguously equal to its design productivity per year while maintaining the above pressure at the inlet to the CS through two gas streams [6,7].

A feature of the operation of the gas processing unit (integrated gas treatment unit) at the current stage of field development is the need to maintain a pressure at the inlet to the installation that ensures the required quality of export gas, i.e. obtaining dew points for water and hydrocarbons established by the gas supply contract.

The current analysis of the parameters of the operation of the IGTU reveals a shortage of reservoir energy of the gas pressure entering the IGTU in the modes corresponding to the design performance.

We note that the overall (integral) effect of gas cooling using low-temperature gas separation technology using regenerative heat exchange largely depends on the type of installed heat exchanger, i.e. its design features and the area of the heat exchange surface [8].

The heat exchangers installed on the IGTU provide an almost twofold decrease in the temperature of the gas entering the low-temperature separator in relation to the Joule-Thompson choke effect.

The formula for determining the required operational value of the gas separation temperature (in a low-temperature separator) is presented as:

$$T_{\text{sep}} = T_{\text{ent.}} - \Delta T_{\text{thr.}} - \Delta T_{\text{TO}}$$

$T_{\text{ent.}}$ is the temperature of the gas at the entrance to the IGTU;

$\Delta T_{\text{thr.}}$ - reducing the temperature on the throttle due to the Joule Thompson effect:

$$\Delta T_{\text{thr.}} = \frac{\Delta P}{\varepsilon}$$

$\Delta P_{\text{thr.}}$ is the pressure drop on the throttle, MPa;

ε is the Joule-Thompson coefficient, determined by the thermodynamic conditions of throttling and assumed to be $\varepsilon = 0.27 \text{ MPa}/^\circ\text{C}$;

ΔT_{O} is a decrease in the temperature of the gas in the heat exchanger, which, according to operational data, is represented as:

$$\Delta T_{\text{thr.}} = 2\Delta T_{\text{thr.}}$$

The critical value of the pressure at the inlet to the IGTU, at which the conditions for the preparation of conditioned gas are met, is determined by the ratio:

$$P_{\text{ent.cr.}} = P_{\text{req.}} + P_{\text{thr.}}$$

where $P_{\text{req.}}$ is the pressure at the beginning of the gas pipeline (at the outlet of the IGTU), which, in turn, is determined depending on the values of the required pressure at the end of the pipeline and pressure losses in the pipeline;

$$P_{\text{req.}} = P_{\text{ter.}} + \Delta P_{\text{gp.}},$$

where: $P_{\text{ter.}}$ is the terminal pressure accepted under the terms of gas supply equal to 5.6 MPa.

As a result of calculations based on the above ratios, the necessary pressure drop at the IGTU to obtain conditioned gas with a dew point on water $T_{\text{d.w.}} = 0^\circ\text{C}$ is in summer $\Delta P \sim 3.0 \text{ MPa}$ and in winter $\Delta P \sim 1.5 - 2.0$, which corresponds to the need to provide at the entrance to the IGTU pressure $P_{\text{ent.}} \sim 9.5 \text{ MPa}$ in summer and 8.5 MPa in winter.

The resources of high-pressure gas, which ensures its preparation to the required conditions at the IGTU, corresponding to the above calculated values of the inlet pressure, are determined in this field development project for the future under consideration [9].

Due to the projected reduction in high-pressure gas resources in the future, in order to maintain the operation of the gas compressor station in modes that ensure gas preparation to export condition, an urgent construction of a booster compressor station is required.

At the Altyguyi field, when choosing the gushing mode (the diameter of the fitting), it is necessary that the well has an optimal flow rate with a small gas factor, gives less water and sand, gushes calmly, without large pulsations. Only when these conditions are met, it is possible to ensure the most rational use of reservoir energy and long-term, uninterrupted gushing of the well.

When choosing the mode of operation of a fountain well, reservoir conditions are also taken into account - the proximity of contour water, the possibility of a plug in the well, the mode of the field itself, etc.

The main reasons for the disruption of the normal operation of fountain wells are the waxing of fountain pipes, the formation of a sand plug, corroding of the fitting, clogging of the fitting or ejection of paraffin complications, etc. [10].

Measures to restore the operation mode of wells are carried out depending on the reason that caused its violation.

When a sand plug is formed in the fountain pipes, which caused the buffer pressure to drop to zero and the supply is stopped, a liquid (oil) pump is flushed into the annular space to restore circulation and eliminate the plug.

A significant decrease in pressure in the annular space indicates the formation of a plug at the bottom and the appearance of water, the latter is detected by taking a sample from the jet. When water appears, it is necessary to increase the pressure on the face by reducing the diameter of the fitting. To eliminate the down-hole plug, the well is allowed to work without a fitting or oil is pumped into the annular space.

The pressure drop on the buffer while increasing the flow rate of the well indicates that the nozzle is corroded by sand, in this case it is necessary to transfer the fountain jet to another outlet and immediately change the nozzle.

If the specified method fails to eliminate sand jams in the lifting pipes or at the bottom, then the well is stopped for repair work, after which it is put into normal operation.

Dewaxing of the elevator is the main way to ensure the normal operation of fountain wells. The largest amount of paraffin is deposited in the upper part of the lifting pipes, at a length of 400 - 1000 m from the well-head and in the field oil collection system, in which paraffin deposition increases during the cold season. Several methods are used against waxing of lifting pipes. First of all, these are regime measures: reduction of pulsation and frequency of gushing, regulation of the gas factor in order to reduce it as much as possible.

If these measures do not give results, it is necessary to clean the lifting pipes from paraffin.

There are 3 types of cleaning from paraffin: mechanical, thermal, chemical [11, 12].

Mechanical cleaning of pipes from paraffin is carried out during the operation of wells without stopping them with scrapers of various designs.

When exposed to heat, the lifting pipes are heated with steam, hot oil pumped into the annulus of the well without stopping it. The melted paraffin is carried out by a jet of oil to the surface, while the paraffin melts in the switch line. The thermal method does not prevent the deposition of paraffin in pipes, it is used sporadically, under favorable conditions and when for some reason it is not possible to use other more effective methods.

As a solvent of paraffin, it is envisaged to use condensate (gasoline), which is extracted at the Altyguyi deposit in sufficient quantities.

The most characteristic complications in gas lift mining are the appearance of sand and cork formation, the deposition of paraffin in lifting pipes and discharge lines.

Measures against sand entering the well are of a regime nature and are reduced to limiting depression, i.e. limiting oil extraction. The amount of liquid extraction from gas lift wells is regulated by changing the amount of injected working agent, the depth of immersion of lifting pipes or their diameter. To prevent the settling of sand during the periods of its greatest inflow from the reservoir, without interrupting operation, oil is pumped into the annulus in small portions by a mobile pump.

Sometimes the pressure of the gas injected into the well increases sharply when the liquid supply is stopped at the same time. This may occur due to the formation of a so-called cartridge sand plug in the lifting pipes, which blocks the section of the lifting pipes, preventing the mixture of oil and injected gas from reaching the surface. To destroy such a plug, gas is pumped not into the annular space, but into lifting pipes. If in this way it is not possible to push the plug from the pipes to the bottom of the well, then it is necessary to remove the pipes [13].

When wells are equipped with a single-row lift, it is finished with a shank of a smaller diameter than the main tubing string. The descent of the lifting pipes with a shank to the filter facilitates the conditions for the removal of sand by the liquid to the surface and prevents the formation of sand jams.

Measures to prevent paraffin deposits in lifting pipes during gas lift operation of wells, and methods for cleaning pipes from paraffin are similar to those used in fountain operation.

With the drop in reservoir pressures and the flooding of reservoirs at some stages of development in the gas condensate fields of the western part of Turkmenistan, it is planned to improve the gas lift. It is proposed to install a column of lifting pipes equipped with borehole chambers with gas lift valves (starting and working) located in them in the production column on the packer. This eliminates the influence of the injected gas

on the flow of liquid into the well. It is planned to conduct research on optimizing the operating modes of gas lift wells according to known methods to determine the optimal flow rate.

It is also necessary to equip the gas lift gas distribution system with regulating and measuring equipment.

All the measures mentioned above are aimed at increasing and stabilizing gas lift production and reducing the volume of injected gas.

At the Altyguyi gas condensate field under development, the number of gas lift wells will increase with the expiration of the operating time, since with the cessation of well gushing, it becomes necessary to transfer them to a mechanized method [14].

Under the existing modes of gas lift lifts, the depth of the input of the working agent (gas) is in the range of 1400 - 3000 m, the gas input into the lift is carried out through holes (punchers) temporarily replacing the working valves.

Gas supply to gas lift wells is carried out from the gas pipeline via separate gas injection lines at operating pressures of 6.2 - 11 MPa.

Operated gas lift wells need to be optimized according to existing methods. According to calculations, in gas lift wells with a gas inlet point of 2300 - 2500, we accept a working pressure of $P_{\text{work}} = 6.4; 7.4; 8.4$ MPa, and in wells with a gas inlet depth of 3000 - 3500 m - 10-12 MPa. At the Altyguyi gas condensate field, it is necessary to implement a closed-cycle compressor gas lift with high-quality gas preparation for the needs of the gas lift and further gas supply to the export gas pipeline.

The issues of ecology and nature protection include restrictions on the external impact on the environment, preventing the loss of hydrocarbon resources during the extraction, carrying out technical and control measures.

Oil and gas enterprises occupy one of the first places among other sectors of the national economy in terms of the degree of environmental impact. Exploration and development of oil fields includes such technologies as exploration drilling, oil production, collection and preparation of hydrocarbons, transportation and processing.

The enterprises of the oil and gas industry have a harmful effect on all objects of nature, the atmosphere, the hydrosphere and underground and surface waters, the geological environment, drilled wells at all depths, on the land where they are located.

The cycle of oil and gas works consists of two main groups:

1. New construction sites (search and exploration, drilling, installation of equipment)
2. Working processes of the enterprise (collection, processing, shipment and processing of oil and gas)

When carrying out construction work, a report is made on technogenic pollution of the earth and the environment for technical reasons.

A report on the measures taken to protect the environment should be prepared by oil and gas producing organizations [15].

It should be noted that the time spent on exploration, drilling and preparation of oil and gas fields, the production time of the enterprise, pollution is caused for technical reasons.

The performance of these works causes high harm to the environment. Ecological catastrophes that occur are physical and mechanical impacts on soil, land, flora, fauna, soil, lowering of hydrogeological conditions, strengthening of soil erosion conditions, deterioration of living conditions of fauna and flora and local residents, and others.

Currently, geological studies have been completed at the Altygyui gas condensate field and a field test plan has been prepared based on the data obtained.

When drilling wells in the fields, the environment is polluted mainly by some chemical elements used in the preparation of drilling fluids.

Currently, normal limit values, chemical elements indicating aggressiveness used in the preparation of drilling fluids have not been established.

During drilling operations, the source of atmospheric air pollution is diesel-fueled equipment that emits 2 tons of hydrocarbons and soot, 30 tons of nitrogen oxides, 8 tons of carbon monoxide and 5 tons of sulfur anhydrite into the atmosphere during the year. When drilling wells, drilling mud is mixed with soil layers, surface and groundwater, forming 30 m³/day of water used [16].

During the development of wells, hydrocarbon mainly causes pollution. In most cases, oil-based circulating solutions with serious environmental consequences produce used wastewater, suspension and colloidal solution.

When preparing environmental protection measures during installation work in wells, it is necessary to avoid work that negatively affects natural objects. Since the sources of pollution are closely related to the technology used by the enterprise, it is necessary to establish the technology that has the least impact on the environment. When geochemical breakdown of the soil, it is necessary to perform the following:

- When preparing plots, it is necessary to prevent contamination of the topsoil from the products obtained;
- To collect sedimentary rocks of drilled rocks on slurry barns;
- It is necessary to cover the slurry barn;
- Restore the soil area of the extracted products;
- Road construction.

As a result of drilling operations, there is a negative impact on the hydrogeological change in the soils of the earth, and as a result, drilling fluids penetrate into aquifers, which lead to the formation of a complex of waters.

The waters used in drilling fluids are divided into three groups:

1. Water formed during the production of works;
2. Water for household work;
3. Atmospheric, rainwater.

Circulating waters are used to carry drilled rocks to the surface. In world practice, 95% of clay elements are mixed into the composition of circulating waters for the preparation of drilling fluids.

The quality of the flushing solutions used helps the speed of drilling operations, the prevention of complications with colmatation and water occurrence [17].

During the operation of producing wells and oil and gas collection facilities, the integrated safety and environmental protection system includes:

- monitoring of the condition of borehole fittings;
- selection of equipment and pipelines that meet the specified operating conditions, taking into account current regulations;
- periodic testing of equipment for strength (crimping);
- corrosion protection;
- prevention of technological complications that create emergency situations (gas communications flooding, deposition of paraffin and salts in wells and collection systems), with the use of special inhibitor substances.

When collecting and storing oil, the requirement of safety and reduction of hydrocarbon emissions into the environment are ensured at the stage of arming assembly points in compliance with building codes and regulations, with the necessary equipment of tanks with floating roofs or breathing valves, with mandatory collapse of tank farms to localize emergency oil spills [18].

When implementing the gas lift method of oil production, with a high manifestation of gas injected into the well to ensure safety and environmental protection, it is envisaged (in addition to the design and construction of the main facilities in full compliance with the required technological parameters of operation according to the current building codes and regulations) the construction and proper operation of additional technological equipment that provides a hydrate-free operation of gas distribution systems (furnaces for heating gas and inhibition unit). In the case of the construction of furnaces for heating hydrocarbons, make a preliminary calculation of atmospheric pollution by combustion products and assess the need to determine the MPC.

Storage and use of chemicals is planned to be carried out in accordance with their individual characteristics and in accordance with Safety Regulations (SR) in the oil industry, including providing employees with personal protective equipment (PPE), carrying out instructions and monitoring the condition of equipment used for the use of chemicals (surfactants, methanol, etc.).

The operation of electrical installations and heating equipment is provided in accordance with the current rules of SR and fire safety rules.

According to estimates, in oil fields with a similar technology of oil extraction and collection, the maximum concentrations of the above harmful substances at the border of the sanitary zone (within a radius of 1000 m from the source of emission) do not exceed the maximum permissible (MPC), which are set for each harmful substance individually according to the methodology of the State Committee for Hydrometeorology (OND-86).

In this regard, emissions of harmful substances into the atmosphere, subject to regular (accident-free) technological modes of operation of oil and gas field

equipment, can be considered approximately corresponding to the maximum permissible emissions (MPI) [19].

A detailed assessment of emissions for all fishing facilities is taken into account when compiling an environmental passport.

The environmental passport is being developed in accordance with GOST 17.0.0.04-90 "System of standards in the field of nature protection and improvement of the use of natural resources", which already gives the full technological cycle of this production from the supply of raw products to the finished product. At the same time, the presence of emissions, discharges and solid waste is carefully checked and calculated at each production facility and their impact on the environment is analyzed. All this material is described and calculated in the relevant chapters of the environmental passport. It also concludes that it is necessary to calculate the norms of MPD, the results of which are issued in the form of a second volume, but in the future, in the event of an increase in oil production due to Miocene-Paleogene and Mesozoic underlying red-colored sediments, it will be necessary to adjust all calculations on emissions.

References

1. Закиров С.Н. Разработка газовых, газоконденсатных месторождений. / М.; –Недра, 1998.
2. Ширковский А.И. Разработка и эксплуатация газовых и газоконденсатных месторождений. / М.; – Недра, 1998.
3. Островский Я.М., Джапаров А. Изучение процессов обводнения нефтяных залежей с помощью характеристик вытеснения. – ТуркменНИИНТИ. Ашгабат. 1980. – с.44.
4. Справочное руководство по проектированию разработки и эксплуатации нефтяных месторождений. // под ред. Гиматудинова. – М: Недра. 1971. – с.342.
5. Инструкция по комплексному исследованию газовых и газоконденсатных пластов и скважин. Зотов Г.А., Алиев Э.С., – М: Недра, 1980г.
6. Инструкция по исследованию газоконденсатных месторождений на газоконденсатность. – М.: Недра, 1975
7. Добыча, подготовка и транспорт природного газа и конденсата. Справ. руководство: в 2 т. / Под ред. Ю.П. Коротаева, Р.Д. Маргудова. – М.: Недра, 1984. – Т. 1.
8. Добыча, подготовка и транспорт природного газа и конденсата. Справ. руководство: в 2 т. – М.: Недра, 1987. Т. II.
9. Вахитов ГГ., Дияшев Р.Н. Анализ результатов исследования скважин месторождения Узень глубинными расходомерами и дебитомерами // Разработка нефтяных месторождений и гидродинамика пласта (Тр. ВНИИнефть). –М.: Недра, 1974. стр. 217-225.
10. Гарипов О.М. Общие тенденции развития высокотехнологичного сервиса при разработке, установке и обслуживании многопакерных систем для одновременно-раздельной эксплуатации / О.М. Гарипов // Нефтяное хозяйство. – 2009. – № 9. стр. 58-61.
11. Геология и разработка крупнейших и уникальных нефтяных и нефтегазовых месторождений России / Под ред. В.Е. Гавуры: в 2-х т.–М.: ВНИИОЭНГ, 1996. -Т.1. стр. 280.
12. Глоговский М. М., Дияшев Р. Я. Определение параметров при совместной эксплуатации пластов по кривым изменения дебита. / Тр. МИНХиГП. Вып. 91. – М.: Недра, 1969.
13. Коротаев Ю.П., Панфилов М.Б., Балашов А.Л., Савченко В.В. Влияние разновременности ввода скважин на конечную отдачу пласта. Теоретический анализ. // Обз. информ. Сер. Разработка и эксплуатация газовых и газоконденсатных месторождений. – М.: ИРЦ Газпром, 1996
14. Максотов Р.А. Разукрупнение объектов разработки для повышения их нефтеотдачи / П.В. Донков, В.А. Леонов, А.В. Сорокин, И.В. Сабанчин // Интенсификация добычи нефти и газа: тр. Международ. технол. симпозиума. –М.: Интернет нефтегазового бизнеса, 2003г.
15. Деряев А.Р. Рекомендации по буровому раствору для бурения секции 215,9 мм открытого ствола наклонно-направленной скважины. // Сборник статей II Международной научно-практической конференции “Наука, общество, технологии: проблемы и перспективы взаимодействия в современном мире”. – Петрозаводск: Научное издание: МЦНП “Новая наука”. 2022. – с.17-22.
16. Деряев А.Р. Рекомендации по борьбе с поглощением при бурении наклонно-направленных скважин. // Сборник статей Международной научно-практической конференции “Инструменты и механизмы современного инновационного развития” – Уфа: Издательство ООО “Омега скайнс”. 2022. – с.62-65.
17. Деряев А.Р. Обоснование принятой методики прогноза технологических показателей разработки нефтяных и нефтегазовых залежей. // Научный журнал “IN SITU” №5/2022 – М: Академическое издательство: “Научная артель”. 2022. – с.24-26.
18. Деряев А.Р. Охрана недр и окружающей среды при разработке газовых месторождений методом одновременной раздельной эксплуатации. // Научный журнал Метод Z №2(4) – Санкт-Петербург: Издательство: ГНИИ «Нацразвитие». 2022.– с.12-14.
19. Derýaýew A.R., Jamiýew M.Ý., Gulatarow H., Mantrowa S.W. Çäklendirilen patent: „Toýunly ergini ingibirlenen termostabilleşdirilen goşundy KAIR-T bilen işläp bejermegiň usuly“. 06.06.2014 ý. senede döwlet tarapyndan reýestre bellige alnan № 604 belgili patent.